

EVALUATION OF IN-VESSEL AND PILOT SCALE COMPOSTING AS AN ALTERNATIVE FOR FOOD WASTE VALORIZATION

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Abstract

Food Residue Biomass (FORBI) is generated by drying and shredding the fermentable fraction of household food waste collected door-to-door in the Municipality of Halandri, Greece. The potential valorization of FORBI for the production of compost is investigated in this work.

Two types of composters were used: an in-vessel composter with an operating volume of 28 L and a pilot-scale composter with a volume of 280 L. Stirring of both composters was carried out once every 24 hours for the homogenization of the substrate and a temperature sensor continuously recorded the temperature evolution of the composting mixture. The maximum temperature of the compost reached up to 52.2 °C for the in-vessel and 67.8 °C for the pilot scale composter, respectively. Additional parameters, such as moisture, pH, electrical conductivity, FAS, TS, VS and TKN, were evaluated.

The experimental results obtained were used as a basis for the development of a model by using the AQUASIM software.

Reference

[1] Kumar, M., Lin, J.G.: Co-composting of Food Waste and Green Waste in Pilot-Scale Systems: In-vessel and Windrow Investigations Dynamic Soil, Dynamic Plant (Special Issue 2), 127-133, Global Science Books. (2011).